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GLUCOCORTICOIDS AND DIABETES

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ABSTRACT

Glucocorticoids (GCs), stress hormones produced by the adrenal cortex, are involved in many physiological and metabolic processes, including glucose homeostasis and inflammation. Excess GC signaling results in Cushing’s syndrome and possibly metabolic syndrome. Diabetes, central adipose tissue, and hyperlipidemia are components of both syndromes. Here, we discuss the mechanisms of GC action, clinical syndromes of GC excess, modulation of glucose homeostasis by GCs, and future GC signaling-based therapies for diabetes.

Keywords: glucocorticoids, insulin resistance, striae, mineralocorticoids, osteoporosis, diabetes mellitus.

INTRODUCTION

Type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM) affects 8.7% of the population of Uzbekistan (WHO 2016) and is associated with multiple microvascular and macrovascular complications. Obesity is a significant risk factor for the development of insulin resistance, which is central to the pathophysiology of type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM). As insulin resistance increases, pancreatic β -cells initially compensate by increasing insulin secretion to maintain normoglycemia. However, over time, β -cells become depleted, leading to insulin deficiency and, subsequently, to the development of diabetes mellitus. The mechanisms underlying insulin resistance remain an active area of research. One of the key factors is adipocyte dysfunction, which occurs in response to chronic nutrient overload. In normal-weight individuals, free fatty acids (FFA) are efficiently sequestered as triglycerides (TG) during periods of caloric excess and released when needed through lipolysis. In obese individuals, adipocytes become dysfunctional, largely due to the inflammatory environment that develops in adipose tissue during prolonged caloric

excess. This condition was first recognized in mouse models of diet-induced obesity and was later confirmed in human studies. As a result, FFA storage is impaired, ectopic lipids accumulate, and serum FFA and inflammatory cytokines are elevated⁶. This leads to systemic insulin resistance. These processes were first recognized in mouse models of diet-induced obesity and were later confirmed in human studies^{4,5}. Glucocorticoids (GCs), also known as stress hormones, play a key role in the regulation of glucose homeostasis, adipocyte development, and inflammatory processes. Glucocorticoid excess, both in clinical settings and in experimental models, is associated with metabolic disorders^{7,8}. Clinical syndromes characterized by elevated glucocorticoid levels are often accompanied by the development of diabetes mellitus and an increase in visceral adipose tissue. Experimental mouse models with localized glucocorticoid excess in adipocytes demonstrate similar metabolic disorders, including the accumulation of visceral adipose tissue and the development of insulin resistance. This review examines the mechanisms regulating glucocorticoid production and metabolism, as well as clinical and basic research supporting their role in the pathogenesis of diabetes mellitus. In addition, the potential of glucocorticoids as a therapeutic target for the treatment of diabetes mellitus is discussed.

REGULATION AND ACTION OF GLUCOCORTICOIDS.

Glucocorticoids (GCs) are steroid hormones produced by the adrenal cortex. Their circulating levels are controlled by the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis, which is a complex neuroendocrine feedback system.

The regulation mechanism includes the following stages:

The hypothalamus produces corticotropin-releasing hormone (CRH), which stimulates the pituitary gland.

The pituitary gland responds by secreting adrenocorticotrophic hormone (ACTH).

ACTH activates the adrenal cortex, stimulating the synthesis and release of cortisol, the main active glucocorticoid in humans.

The HPA axis is activated in response to stress, circadian rhythms, and other acute stimuli. Circulating cortisol exerts negative feedback by suppressing the production of CRH and ACTH, which reduces further cortisol production. Only about 5% of cortisol circulates in a free, biologically active form. The remainder is bound to carrier proteins such as cortisol-binding globulin (CBG) and albumin⁹. These proteins mediate the transport of cortisol within tissues and regulate its availability. The action of glucocorticoids (GCs) is mediated by two types of receptors: glucocorticoid (GR) and mineralocorticoid (MR). Although GCs and mineralocorticoids such as aldosterone bind MRs with equal affinity, circulating GC concentrations are much higher than aldosterone concentrations. This raises the question: how do mineralocorticoid-sensitive tissues

maintain selective sensitivity to aldosterone? A key role in this specific regulation is played by the 11 β -hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase (11 β -HSDH) enzyme system:

11 β -HSDH2 is expressed predominantly in mineralocorticoid-sensitive tissues such as the kidney. This enzyme inactivates cortisol by converting it to cortisone, which cannot activate MR. This prevents excessive activation of MR by glucocorticoids and allows aldosterone to effectively perform its function.

In contrast, 11 β -HSDH1 is expressed in metabolically active tissues such as the liver and adipose tissue. This enzyme catalyzes the reverse reaction, activating cortisone and converting it to cortisol. This activation plays an important role in the pathophysiology of metabolic syndrome.

Most of the metabolic effects of glucocorticoids, including their effects on glucose homeostasis, are mediated through activation of glucocorticoid receptors (GR)^{9,10}.

The glucocorticoid receptor (GR) belongs to a family of nuclear hormone receptors involved in transcription regulation. Binding of glucocorticoids (GC) to GR triggers several key processes:

Dissociation of the cytosolic complex: When GC binds to GR, the receptor is released from its cytosolic complex, which includes heat shock protein (HSP90).

Nuclear translocation: Released GH translocates to the cell nucleus where it interacts with DNA to regulate the transcription of target genes.

In the nucleus, GR regulates transcription in two main ways:

Transcriptional activation: GH binds to glucocorticoid response elements (GREs) in the promoter regions of genes and interacts with transcriptional coactivators to enhance the expression of target genes.

Transcriptional repression: The repressive effect is realized through two mechanisms:

GH binds to ERGH and then interacts with transcriptional corepressors, suppressing the expression of certain genes.

Direct interaction of GR with other transcription factors without the involvement of DNA (DNA-independent mechanism), a process known as "tethering".

These mechanisms allow GH to exert complex effects on gene expression, regulating multiple processes including metabolism, inflammation, and immune response¹¹.

Clinical and subclinical glucocorticoid excess

Chronic glucocorticoid excess is associated with the development of Cushing's syndrome (CS), a serious clinical condition characterized by a wide range of symptoms and complications.

Clinical manifestations of Cushing's syndrome

SC is characterized by the following features:

Metabolic disorders:central obesity, insulin resistance and/or diabetes mellitus.

Muscle and bone changes:muscle atrophy and loss of bone mass (osteoporosis).

Dermatological signs:hyperpigmented abdominal striae, thinning skin, delayed wound healing.

Cardiovascular and neuropsychological disorders:resistant hypertension, as well as depression, anxiety and cognitive impairment.

Diagnosis of Cushing's syndrome

Diagnosis of SC is a complex process that requires a combination of clinical and laboratory methods. The main diagnostic approaches include:

Measuring Salivary Cortisol Levels at Midnight:SC is characterized by the absence of the normal circadian rhythm of cortisol, which normally reaches its minimum values at night.

Overnight dexamethasone test:Administration of exogenous glucocorticoid (dexamethasone) allows one to evaluate the suppression of endogenous cortisol production. The absence of suppression indicates hypercorticism.

Measurement of 24-hour urinary free cortisol:Elevated free cortisol levels confirm hypercortisolism^{12,13}.

Glucocorticoids (GC)are widely used to treat various autoimmune diseases due to their powerful anti-inflammatory properties. However, long-term therapy with exogenous GCs remains the most common cause of Cushing's syndrome (CS).

Types of Cushing's syndrome associated with endogenous GCs

SC caused by hyperproduction of endogenous GC is divided into:

ACTH-dependent SC

The most common cause is a pituitary adenoma that secretes adrenocorticotrophic hormone (ACTH).

Rarely, KS can be caused by neuroendocrine tumors that secrete ACTH, such as:

Small cell lung cancer(classic example).

Other neuroendocrine tumors.

ACTH-independent SC

It is less common and is caused by direct hyperproduction of cortisol by the adrenal glands.

Main reasons:

Adrenal adenoma.

Adrenal cortex hyperplasia.

These differences in the mechanisms of KS development highlight the importance of accurate diagnosis to identify the underlying cause of the disease, since treatment approaches depend on the specific source of hypercortisolism^{12,13}.

The influence of glucocorticoids (GC) on glucose metabolism and diabetes diagnosis

Glucocorticoids significantly increase postprandial glucose excursion, suggesting that diagnostic methods such as hemoglobin A1C testing and oral glucose tolerance testing may be more useful for diagnosing GC therapy-induced diabetes¹⁴.

However, it has been noted that there is a positive correlation between fasting plasma glucose and morning plasma cortisol levels, indicating that abnormal fasting glucose values are more common in individuals with more severe hypercortisolemia¹⁵.

Effect of dose and duration of exogenous GC therapy on the development of diabetes

With long-term use of exogenous GCs, the likelihood of developing diabetes is proportional to the dose and duration of therapy. Case-control studies have shown that after initiation of GC therapy, the likelihood of developing new diabetes increases more than twofold compared with the control group. This effect is dose-dependent:

2 mg dexamethasone:The odds ratio for developing diabetes is 3.06.

4 mg dexamethasone:probability coefficient 5.90.

4.5 mg or more of dexamethasone:probability coefficient 10.35.

For comparison, a healthy person synthesizes the equivalent of 0.55 mg dexamethasone per day^{16,17}.

The increased incidence of diabetes in patients receiving exogenous GCs also has an impact on mortality, which is twice as high in such patients. This highlights the importance of blood sugar control and close monitoring in patients receiving long-term GC therapy¹².

Indeed, exogenous glucocorticoids such as dexamethasone, prednisone or hydrocortisone have a significant effect on carbohydrate metabolism and glycemic control in patients with diabetes, which is associated with increased insulin resistance and elevated blood glucose levels. Your text highlights several important aspects:

Increased insulin requirements: In diabetic patients receiving glucocorticoids, insulin requirements increase, sometimes by 70% or more, depending on the dose and duration of therapy. For example, a study using 60 mg prednisone (equivalent to 240 mg hydrocortisone) showed a 70% increase in insulin requirements. This is important to consider when adjusting insulin doses in these patients to prevent hyperglycemia and improve disease control.²²

Hyperglycemia and relapses: In the hospital setting where patients receive exogenous glucocorticoids, hyperglycemia occurs in more than half of patients, and many experience relapses of hyperglycemia. This highlights the importance of regular glucose monitoring and the possible need for insulin dose adjustments, particularly in patients receiving high doses of steroids.

Circadian changes in glycemic control: Using continuous glucose monitoring helps to identify patterns in glucose levels throughout the day. Hyperglycemia is more common in the afternoon and evening, which may justify the use of higher doses of prandial insulin or the addition of NPH insulin, which is active at peak levels between 6 and 8 a.m. This allows for more accurate control of glucose levels during periods when they are most susceptible to fluctuations^{18,20,21}.

Individualization of therapy: Because of the wide variation in glucocorticoid responses and doses, it is important to individualize insulin therapy taking these factors into account. Patients with type 1 diabetes taking steroids may require significant insulin dose adjustments, including in response to acute conditions or changes in glucocorticoid dose.

In general, therapy of diabetes in patients receiving exogenous glucocorticoids requires careful monitoring and flexible adjustment of insulin doses to prevent hyperglycemia and maintain optimal glucose control.

CS is a rare disease, with an incidence of approximately seven per million people in Uzbekistan. However, the description of metabolic syndrome (MetS),²³ a condition that affects almost a quarter of the adult population and is characterized by obesity, hyperlipidemia, and insulin resistance,²⁴ has led to the suggestion that MetS may represent a subset of patients with CS or subclinical CS (SCS). SCS is most often associated with cortisol-producing adrenal adenomas rather than pituitary Cushing's disease, and is characterized by mild hypercortisolism and metabolic disturbances, including obesity, hypertension, and insulin resistance, without the classic clinical features of CS. Notably, the incidence of clinical hypercortisolism in individuals with diabetes or CVD has been reported to be 3–10% of the total number of subjects examined.²⁵

Strong associations between circulating cortisol levels and features of MetS have been demonstrated. Although some have observed subtle changes in HPA axis activity in patients with MetS, these cannot fully explain the etiology of MetS²⁶. However, the description of tissue-specific conversion of inactive GCs to active GCs by 11 β HSD1 in tissues prone to GC-induced insulin resistance has revived interest in GCs as a primary cause of the etiology of MetS. Indeed, rodent models using targeted overexpression of 11 β HSD1 in adipocytes exhibit a phenotype similar to MetS, characterized by insulin resistance, hyperlipidemia, and visceral fat mass⁸. Furthermore, human studies have shown a correlation between the expression of adipocyte 11 β HSDH1 and intra-abdominal fat levels, as well as worsening insulin sensitivity²⁷. These findings have led to the development of the so-called "dehydrogenase hypothesis" to explain the tissue-specific enhancement of GC action as a mechanism for the development of tissue-specific Cushing's syndrome and systemic metabolic syndrome^{28,29}.

Regulation of glucose metabolism by glucocorticoids

Glucocorticoids affect all aspects of glucose metabolism, interacting with the liver, the endocrine system of the pancreas, skeletal muscle, and adipose tissue. They counteract the action of insulin. The catabolic effects of excess glucocorticoids promote the release of energy reserves. In the short term, such effects play a key role in adaptation to acute stress or illness, helping to maintain circulating glucose levels and ensuring continued brain function.

The long-term consequences of glucocorticoid (GC) excess, as noted, include hyperglycemia and insulin resistance. The effects of GC excess on various tissues will be discussed in the context of glucose utilization, gluconeogenesis, glycogen metabolism, and pancreatic endocrine function 30.

Figure 1

Gluconeogenic pathway in hepatocytes. Gluconeogen precursors (lactate and alanine) are converted to pyruvate, which enters the mitochondria and is converted to oxaloacetate (OAA) by pyruvate carboxylase. OAA exits the mitochondria via the malate-aspartate shuttle to form phosphoenolpyruvate (PEP). OAA can also be converted to PEP directly in the mitochondria. PEP then enters the gluconeogenic pathway. In addition, glycerol is metabolized to dihydroxyacetone phosphate (DHAP), which is then converted

to fructose 1,6-bisphosphate (F1,6BP). The final product, glucose, is formed in the ER by the catalytic subunit of glucose 6-phosphatase (G6PC). Key enzymes are boxed, and major GR targets are shown in yellow. Abbreviations: OAA oxaloacetate, PEP phosphoenolpyruvate, DHAP dihydroxyacetone phosphate, G3P glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate, F1,6BP fructose 1,6-bisphosphate, 2-PG 2-phosphoglycerate, 3-PG 3-phosphoglycerate, 1,3-BPG

1,3-bisphosphoglycerate, G3P glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate, F1,6BP fructose 1,6-bisphosphate, F6P fructose 6-phosphate and G6P glucose 6-phosphate. Enzyme abbreviations: PC pyruvate carboxylase, m-PCK1 mitochondrial phosphoenolpyruvate carboxykinase, PCK1 cytosolic phosphoenolpyruvate carboxykinase, FBP1 fructose-1,6-bisphosphatase 1, PFK1 phosphofructokinase 1, G6PC glucose 6-phosphatase catalytic subunit.

Gluconeogenesis, which occurs primarily in the liver, is the process of synthesizing glucose from non-carbohydrate substrates such as lactate, glycerol, and amino acids. This review does not cover the entire gluconeogenic pathway in detail, but will outline the major steps regulated by glucocorticoids (see Fig. 1). Glucocorticoids play an important role in the formation of gluconeogenic precursors by activating lipolysis in adipose tissue and protein breakdown in muscle, resulting in the formation of glycerol and amino acids required for glucose synthesis^{30,32}. GCs also stimulate gluconeogenesis by activating the binding of glucocorticoid receptors to glucocorticoid response elements in the promoter regions of genes encoding enzymes such as glucose-6-phosphatase and phosphoenolpyruvate carboxykinase, key enzymes in gluconeogenesis^{30,31}.

Regulation of glycogen metabolism differs from gluconeogenesis because it is tissue-specific. In the liver, glucocorticoids stimulate glycogen formation by increasing the activity of glycogen synthase, while in skeletal muscle they decrease glycogen synthesis by decreasing the activity of the same enzyme^{30,33}.

Utilization and oxidation of glucose in white adipose tissue and skeletal muscle is dependent on insulin signaling. Glucocorticoids antagonize insulin signaling in skeletal muscle, in particular by reducing GLUT4 translocation to the cell membrane^{30,34}. In addition, GCs contribute to the development of insulin resistance by regulating several glucocorticoid receptor target genes, which leads to impaired insulin signaling and decreased activity of phosphoinositide 3-kinase and AKT^{35,36}. GCs also stimulate the formation of lipid mediators such as fatty acids from adipocytes and ceramides from the liver, which may contribute to systemic insulin resistance^{6,30,37}.

The mechanisms by which GCs influence glucose utilization in adipocytes are less clear, but likely involve modulation of GLUT4 function and insulin signaling pathways³⁰. Glucocorticoids are also involved in the differentiation and expansion of

adipocyte precursors, which may exacerbate insulin resistance and adipocyte dysfunction^{30,38}.

Glucocorticoids (GCs) have a significant effect on pancreatic β -cells, and their action differs in vivo and in vitro:

In vivo:

Under the influence of GC, secondary hyperplasia of β -cells is observed, which is an adaptive response of the body to maintain normal glucose levels in conditions of peripheral insulin resistance.

In vitro:

In isolated islet experiments, GCs directly induce β -cell apoptosis, which is inconsistent with the adaptive effects observed in vivo³⁰.

Impaired glucose-stimulated insulin secretion (GSIS):

GCs reduce the amount of GLUT2 transporter and glucokinase levels, which slows down the conversion of glucose to glucose-6-phosphate (G6P).

Glucose-6-phosphatase activity increases, which further limits the entry of G6P into the glycolytic cycle.

These changes decrease the ATP/ADP ratio, suppress membrane depolarization, reduce calcium influx, and interfere with insulin exocytosis.

Effect on potassium channels:

GCs enhance the activity of the potassium channel Kv1.5, which promotes repolarization of β -cells, reducing the influx of calcium and inhibiting insulin secretion.

Transgenic mouse models:

Overexpression of glucocorticoid receptors in β -cells leads to deterioration of glucose tolerance and impaired insulin secretion, which confirms the negative effect of GC on β -cells.

Thus, GCs have a complex effect on β -cells, inhibiting key mechanisms of insulin secretion, which explains their association with an increased risk of developing type 2 diabetes.

Summary and Future Directions

Glucocorticoids (GCs) play an important and multifaceted role in the regulation of glucose metabolism. This review examines their mechanisms of action, regulatory features, and clinical and subclinical conditions associated with excess GCs, including their impact on glucose homeostasis.

Short-term and long-term effects:

Increased GC levels during stress play a protective role, but their chronic excess (endogenous or exogenous) is associated with many complications.

Overt GC excess is observed in Cushing's syndrome (CS), whereas subclinical excess is typical for patients with metabolic syndrome.

Research into new therapies:

Selective glucocorticoid receptor modulators (SGRMs) are being developed to treat complications of GC excess, such as insulin resistance and diabetes mellitus (DM).

SMGRs aim to exploit the anti-inflammatory properties of GCs while minimizing their negative metabolic consequences. However, the complexity of development is associated with the intersection of receptor transactivation and transrepression mechanisms.

Modern drugs:

Mifepristone, a GC antagonist, is already used to treat CS in patients with glucose intolerance and diabetes when surgery has failed.

The use of systemic GC antagonists in patients without GC excess is limited due to the risk of developing adrenal insufficiency.

New approaches in diabetes therapy:

Liver-specific GC antagonists coupled to bile acids are being developed to reduce gluconeogenesis without affecting the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis.

Antisense oligonucleotides targeting HA receptor mRNA in the liver are another promising approach.

11 β -hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase 1 (11 β -HSDH1) inhibitors have been shown to be effective in improving insulin sensitivity and lowering blood glucose levels, but their long-term effects on the immune and endocrine systems remain unclear.

Prospects:

The relationship between GC and diabetes remains complex and poorly understood.

GCs influence the regulation of glucose metabolism in various organs, antagonizing the effects of insulin both directly and indirectly.

Increased research into tissue-specific modulation of GC signaling may lead to significant advances in the understanding and treatment of metabolic disorders.

Development of technologies and methods for studying the specific effects of GC in various tissues will likely provide new opportunities for the treatment of diabetes and metabolic syndrome.

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